

POLITICAL SCIENCES

CONFLICT THEORY AND THE INTERPRETATION OF COVID-19: STRUGGLE FOR RESOURCES AND SOCIAL JUSTICE

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Abstract

Using conflict theory as a key sociological approach, it analyzes how the coronavirus has intensified the struggle for power and resources. Through conflict theory, we can clearly see that COVID-19 has exacerbated existing inequalities and conflicts in the economy and society as a whole. The COVID-19 pandemic has not only exposed the health deficiencies of societies around the world, but has also upended the international political scene, increasing existing conflicts and tensions.

Keywords: conflict, struggle, resources, power, vaccines, diplomacy, cooperation.

Introduction

In the world of sociology, conflict theory focuses on understanding social injustices, power, and the struggle for resources. With the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic, conflict theorists have examined how the virus has affected different social groups and how it has exacerbated existing social inequalities and conflicts.

Conflict theory is a key sociological approach that analyzes society through a focus on the contradictions, tensions, and conflicts that arise due to the unequal distribution of resources and power. This theory focuses on the dynamics of dominance and subordination in social and institutional relations and emphasizes conflict as a driver of social change.

Basic concepts and principles of conflict theory include:

1. Inequality of resources and power: Conflict theory examines how different groups and individuals struggle for limited resources, power and influence, and how this leads to different forms of dominance and exploitation.
2. The dynamics of conflict: This approach analyzes how conflicts lead to changes in social structures and relations, focusing on the processes of mobilization, organization and social struggle.
3. The Role of Ideology: Conflict theory considers the role of ideology and dominant ideas as the means by which certain groups strengthen and maintain their position and power.
4. Social change: This approach considers conflict as a key mechanism of social change and development, focusing on how contradictions and struggles lead to the transformation of social relations and structures.

Leaving aside Marxist views, a number of scholars have contributed to the development of this theory.

Max Weber expands the concept of conflict beyond the realm of economics. It also examines other dimensions of social inequality, such as status and power, and emphasizes the importance of ideology and beliefs in social relations.

Lewis Coser emphasizes that conflict can also have stabilizing functions in society and does not always lead to disintegration and destruction. He considers conflict a normal aspect of social relations and emphasizes its potential for social change and adaptation.

Ralph Dahrendorf focused attention on the structures of power and authority in society. It analyzes how power is distributed and how this leads to conflicts and contradictions in social institutions.

Through the prism of this theory, the following aspects of the crisis caused by the corona virus could be considered: struggle for resources and power; vaccines as a means of influence; medical resources and deepening social inequality; economic consequences and international cooperation.

Vaccines: A vehicle for power and influence

The coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic has put vaccines at the center of global attention, presenting them as the primary means of combating the spread of the virus. Vaccines, however, have not only become a tool for preventing disease and saving lives; they have also become a means of power and influence that is used in political, economic and geopolitical contexts.

An example of the use of vaccines as a means of power and influence can be the case of "vaccine diplomacy" (Felter, 2021) practiced by some countries, including Russia and China. These countries have been actively marketing their vaccines to various countries, especially those that have difficulty accessing vaccines produced in the West. This approach allows these countries to impose influence, strengthen political ties and show global leadership in the fight against the pandemic.

The development, production and distribution of vaccines have been the subject of intense political debates and decisions. Political leaders and governments tried to assert their authority and competence by coordinating their response to the pandemic, including providing vaccines to their citizens.

The example of the European Union (EU) can be used to illustrate this point. In January and February 2021, there was intense political activity and debate at EU level in relation to the spread of vaccines against COVID-19. At the center of the debates were issues related to the speed of approval, delivery and distribution of vaccines among member states.

Certain countries have expressed dissatisfaction with the slow pace and uneven distribution of vaccines. The Commission and some Member States insisted on solidarity and a coordinated approach, while other

countries sought bilateral agreements outside the common EU framework to speed up the receipt of vaccines for their citizens.

This example shows how political leaders and governments tried to assert their authority and competence by coordinating their response to the pandemic. It also illustrates how vaccine production and distribution were the subject of intense political debates and decisions at national and international levels.

Vaccines have become a tool on the geopolitical stage, where various countries and blocs have tried to increase their influence and diplomatic status. "Vaccine diplomacy" became an expression symbolizing the aid and distribution of vaccines as a means of strengthening international relations and partnerships.

One of the vivid examples of "vaccine diplomacy" is the actions of China. Chinese authorities are actively providing their COVID-19 vaccines to various countries, especially in the developing world, including Africa, Latin America and parts of Asia.

In the first half of 2021, China dosed or discounted millions of doses of its vaccines in multiple countries. This not only helped these countries speed up their vaccination campaigns, but also strengthened China's diplomatic position and increased its influence in these regions. China's "vaccine diplomacy" also underscores the country's strategy to strengthen international relations and partnerships by providing aid and resources during the pandemic.

This approach allows China to demonstrate global leadership, humanitarian commitment and the ability to provide concrete solutions in response to the global crisis, which can contribute to improving the country's international image and strengthening diplomatic ties.

Pharmaceutical companies and national economies entered into intense competition to develop, manufacture and distribute vaccines. Innovation and research were stimulated, but they were also subject to economic struggle and competition for market shares and influence.

An example of this claim would be the competition between pharmaceutical giants Pfizer/BioNTech, Moderna and AstraZeneca/Oxford, which developed some of the first and most widespread vaccines against COVID-19.

1. Innovation and research:

- Pfizer/BioNTech and Moderna rapidly developed vaccines using new mRNA technology, while AstraZeneca/Oxford used adenovirus vector technology.

2. Encouraging competition:

- The race to rapidly develop, test and mass produce vaccines has resulted in several vaccines being developed in record time (less than a year), an unprecedented achievement in medicine.

3. Economic struggle and competition:

- Each of these manufacturers sought to increase their market share by speeding up production and delivery, as well as by emphasizing different aspects such as efficacy, storage and cost of their vaccines.

- For example, Pfizer and Moderna have set higher prices for their vaccines, while AstraZeneca has announced that it will provide its vaccine "on a stand-alone basis" during the pandemic.

Vaccines have also created social divisions and ethical questions related to access to vaccination, forced vaccination and discrimination. This created public debates and conflicts about the management of the pandemic and the use of vaccines.

One specific example that demonstrates the social divisions and ethical issues surrounding vaccines is the introduction of "green certificates" or COVID passports in various countries, including parts of the European Union.

1. Access to vaccination:

- The introduction of COVID passports, which confirm vaccination, recovery from COVID-19 or a negative test, created a divide between the vaccinated and the unvaccinated, with the latter being restricted in their access to certain services, for example travel, hospital admission without a certificate, etc.

2. Forced vaccination:

- Some countries or organizations may have imposed vaccination requirements for access to certain workplaces, schools or travel, which also raises debates about compulsory vaccination and individual rights and freedoms.

3. Discrimination:

- COVID passports have led to discrimination, with the unvaccinated or people who for various reasons cannot be vaccinated being at risk of exclusion from certain social, cultural or economic activities.

This example shows that managing the pandemic through vaccination can create social divisions and give rise to ethical questions and debates about rights, freedoms and discrimination.

The coronavirus pandemic has placed vaccines at the center of the global stages of power and influence, making it clear that they are not only a medical product, but also a key resource and tool in modern societies and international relations.

Medical Resources: Limited Access and Competition

The COVID-19 pandemic has mercilessly exposed the shortcomings and limitations of healthcare systems around the world. In times of crisis, medical resources – from medicines, medical equipment to health workers – were limited, and this led to competition and struggle for their access and distribution.

The lack of sufficient medical resources such as protective gear, respirators, and tests for the coronavirus has become a critical issue. Many countries and regions faced difficulties in trying to meet the growing demand, which posed serious obstacles to the effective response of health systems to the pandemic.

Countries and regions that have faced problems in their response to the COVID-19 pandemic:

1. The United States:

- At the start of the pandemic, many states faced shortages of medical equipment such as respirators and protective gear. Also, there was the issue of the tests being limited.

2. Italy:

• It was among the worst affected countries in the first months of the pandemic. Hospitals were overburdened, and medical staff were exhausted and inadequately protected.

3. Spain:

• Like Italy, Spain has faced a huge shortage of medical equipment and problems with the capacity of the health system to cope with the high number of patients.

4. Brazil:

• Shortages of resources, including protective gear and respirators, have affected the country's response to the pandemic, particularly in some remote areas.

5. India:

• Despite being a major producer of medical products, India also faced problems in the supply of oxidizer and other medical materials during the COVID-19 waves.

Areas in which the crisis occurred:

- Logistics:
 - Multiple countries had problems with the logistics and distribution of medical supplies and equipment.
- Production:
 - The ability of many countries to produce the necessary materials was limited or inadequate to demand.
- Financial resources:
 - Lack of financial resources made it difficult to purchase the necessary medical products from some countries.
- Human Resources:
 - Medical staff were overstretched and in many places there was a shortage of trained staff.
- Coordination and communication:
 - Coordination and communication problems between different levels of government and health institutions were also visible in many countries.

Each of these issues contributed to the difficulties faced by many countries during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The countries have entered into what can be described as a "global competition" for medical resources. Demand for equipment, materials and vaccines in international markets has increased, and competition between different countries and regions has intensified sharply.

The struggle for medical resources also had its political consequences, including tensions, conflicts and changes in international relations. She emphasized the need for better coordination, cooperation and solidarity at the global level.

One specific example that highlights the struggle for medical resources and its political consequences is the competition and tension between different countries to obtain medical equipment and supplies, including protective gear and respirators, at the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Example: US and Canada - Conflict over N95 Masks (Forbes, 2020)

• Situation: In April 2020, it was reported that the US administration has suspended the export of N95 masks manufactured by the 3M company to Canada and Latin America. This decision was made to ensure

that enough masks are available for healthcare workers in the US.

• Political Implications:

• The decision sparked fierce reactions from Canada, with Prime Minister Justin Trudeau warning that "blocking medical supplies is something that will have serious consequences on both sides of the border."

• In response, the US administration and the 3M company reached an agreement on the free export of masks, but this incident left a mark on bilateral relations and highlighted the need for better international coordination and cooperation.

This example shows that shortages in medical resources can have direct political and diplomatic consequences, and highlights the importance of international cooperation in global health crises.

The economic struggle caused by COVID-19, through the lens of conflict theory

Through the lens of conflict theory, which analyzes the struggle for resources and power in society, we can look at how the pandemic affected different socio-economic groups and how this highlighted existing social and economic inequalities.

Widening gap between rich and poor:

The COVID-19 pandemic has left a deep mark on global societies and economies, but one of its most worrying consequences is the increase in social and economic inequalities. The gap between the rich and the poor, which was already significant, widened even more during the crisis. Here is a specific example based on statistics:

Example: Impact of Unemployment in the US

Data from the US Bureau of Labor Statistics (BLS) (Survey, 2020):

- In April 2020, US unemployment jumped to 14.7%, the highest level since the Great Depression.
- Particularly hard hit were low-income workers in sectors such as restaurants and tourism, which were hit hard by pandemic restrictions.

Socio-Economic Differences (center, 2021):

• According to the Pew Research Center, 39% of those working in households with annual incomes below \$40,000 had lost their jobs or had their wages cut as of March 2020.

• At the same time, many of the wealthy households had the option of working from home, which reduced the impact on their economic situation.

Rift Expansion:

• According to a report by the Economic Policy Institute (workers, 2022), the average income of the top 1% of earners has been about 5 times greater than the income of the bottom 90% in recent decades. This inequality is expected to deepen further as a result of the pandemic.

This example highlights the fact that the COVID-19 pandemic has undoubtedly contributed to the increase in social and economic inequalities, making life even more difficult for already vulnerable and disadvantaged groups in society.

Reasons for widening the rift are as follows. Loss of jobs and income: Many people in low-paying sectors lost their jobs or faced a reduction in their income due to the restrictions and lockdowns.

The example I will give is based on statistics from the US, but similar trends have been observed in many countries around the world.

Example: Loss of jobs in the US restaurant sector

Data from the US Bureau of Labor Statistics (BLS (Survey, 2020)):

- In April 2020, the US restaurant and hospitality sector lost over 5.5 million jobs.
- The leisure and hospitality sector, which includes restaurants and hotels, was the hardest hit, accounting for nearly 40% of job losses in April.

Additional data:

- According to research by the National Restaurant Association (Association, 2021), 17% of restaurants in the US were temporarily or permanently closed as of December 2020, corresponding to about 110,000 establishments.
- The same organization reported that the restaurant and catering industry lost a total of \$240 billion in 2020 compared to pre-pandemic expectations.

This example clearly shows that austerity measures and lock-downs have had a devastating impact on low-paying sectors such as the restaurant industry, leading to a massive loss of jobs and income.

Consequences

- Educational disparities: Children from poor families had less access to online education, which hampered their academic development.
- Health disparities: The poor had less access to medical services and vaccines, increasing their vulnerability to the virus.
- Increase in poverty: Many people fell into poverty or at risk of poverty due to the loss of jobs and income.

COVID-19 has not only exposed but also reinforced existing social and economic inequalities. Tackling this growing divide requires a targeted and solidarity-based policy that supports vulnerable groups and works to create a more equal and just society.

Sectors such as tourism, hospitality and the arts have been particularly affected by pandemic restrictions, leading to mass layoffs and layoffs. At the same time, sectors such as technology and pharmaceuticals flourished as their products and services became increasingly necessary.

Telecommuting became the new "normal" for many, but this option was not available to all workers. This created new forms of division in the labor market, where some could work safely from home while others were at risk of contagion.

Many SMEs have suffered badly or even gone bankrupt due to the restrictions and economic uncertainty. This, in turn, led to market consolidation in favor of large corporations.

Through conflict theory, we can clearly see that COVID-19 has exacerbated existing inequalities and conflicts in the economy and society as a whole. The pandemic presents a challenge that requires collective efforts and solidarity to reduce its long-term negative effects and create a fairer and more sustainable economic model in the future.

Political Conflict and COVID-19: A Wave of Challenges and Opportunities

The COVID-19 pandemic has not only exposed the health deficiencies of societies around the world, but has also upended the international political scene, igniting new and exacerbating existing conflicts and tensions. The global crisis has become a test of international solidarity and cooperation, highlighting in many cases the competitive aspects of relations between states.

Intensification of conflicts

- Geopolitical realignments: In response to the pandemic, many countries focused on national interests by introducing border closures and restrictions on the export of medical products, which affected international relations and cooperation.

Intensification of conflicts and geopolitical restructuring

Example of conflicts and restructurings:

USA and China:

- Conflict: Rhetoric between the US and China has intensified during the pandemic, particularly around the origin of the virus and the management of the pandemic. This included accusations by the then US leadership of China's lack of transparency regarding COVID-19.

- Geopolitical realignments: There have also been heightened tensions around trade ties and technological sovereignty, with the US trying to limit Chinese technological influence (eg Huawei).

European Union:

- Focus on national interests: At the start of the pandemic, some EU member states introduced border controls and restrictions on the export of medical supplies, such as masks and respirators, which caused tensions between the allies.

• Impact on international relations: These actions have shown the difficulties in coordinating a common response in times of crisis, leading to talk of the need for a more solidarity and unified approach in the future.

"Vaccine Nationalism":

- Countries such as the US, UK and other rich nations have focused on securing sufficient quantities of vaccines for their own populations, often through advance contracts with pharmaceutical companies, which has affected the global distribution of vaccines and put at risk lower-income countries dependent on from international initiatives such as COVAX.

Russia and "vaccine diplomacy":

- Russia is using its Sputnik V vaccine as a tool of diplomacy, offering access to it to countries in Eastern Europe, Latin America and Asia, in order to strengthen its geopolitical position and influence.

These examples illustrate how national interest and the drive for self-sufficiency can cause changes in international relations, intensify existing conflicts, and force a restructuring of geopolitical alliances and cooperation.

- Economic nationalism: With the decline in the world economy, many countries began to look for ways to protect themselves, which often involved behavior contrary to international norms and cooperation.

Economic nationalism during the COVID-19 pandemic has manifested itself in several main ways:

- **Protection of domestic production and jobs:** Countries introduced measures to support their national economies, which included financial assistance for affected businesses and the preservation of jobs in critical industries.

- **Restrictions on the export of medical equipment and medicines:** At the beginning of the pandemic, many countries banned or restricted the export of essential medical equipment such as masks, respirators and other personal protective equipment to ensure that there were enough stocks for their own needs.

- **Favoring the domestic market:** Stimulating domestic consumption became a priority, encouraging citizens to buy products produced in their own country to support the national economy.

- **Strategic reorientation of production:** Some countries have begun to strategically shift their production lines to meet the needs of essential medical goods, which includes developing domestic vaccine production capabilities.

- **National vaccination strategies:** Vaccination strategies often focused first on the national population before considering international aid or export, leading to the term "vaccine nationalism".

- **Rethinking global supply chains:** The pandemic has prompted a rethinking of global supply chains and encouraging the return of production to the home country to reduce the risks of disruptions in the future.

- **Investment Controls:** Some countries have introduced tighter controls on foreign investment, especially in key industries, to prevent the buyout of important national assets by foreign companies at a time of economic uncertainty.

- **Support for domestic innovation and development:** Governments invested in research and development of new technologies in the country to accelerate the creation of domestic solutions to the pandemic.

- **Technological and information warfare:** The pandemic has accelerated technological change and competition, while also becoming the subject of information warfare and disinformation directed at competing nations. The term "hybrid warfare" refers to a strategy that combines conventional military tactics with non-military tactics, such as cyberattacks, disinformation, and economic pressure. During the COVID-19 pandemic, some analysts and politicians have accused various countries of using hybrid warfare tactics, often in the context of information wars or influence wars. An example of such behavior could be the campaign of disinformation related to the origin and spread of the virus, as well as the efficacy and safety of various vaccines. For example, there are reports that Russia and China have used their media and social networks to spread misinformation about vaccines developed by Western countries to undermine confidence in them and promote their own vaccines as an alternative. These actions could be interpreted as part of hybrid warfare, aiming to promote division within certain countries or between allies, to undermine trust in authorities and

health systems, to promote one's own political and economic agenda, and to end up influence on the international scene.

Conclusion

The pandemic as an opportunity for cooperation

- **Joint vaccine development efforts:** Despite the conflicts, we have also seen examples of international cooperation, especially in the field of vaccine research and development. An example of international collaboration in research and vaccine development during the COVID-19 pandemic is the global COVAX initiative. It is part of the Access to COVID-19 Tools (ACT) Accelerator and a collaboration led by Gavi (the Vaccine Alliance), the Coalition for Epidemic Preparedness (CEPI) and the World Health Organization (WHO). It seeks to accelerate the development and production of vaccines against COVID-19 and to ensure fair and equal access to them for all countries of the world, regardless of their economic status. In doing so, COVAX brought together governments, global health organizations, vaccine manufacturers, the private sector, civil society and others to create a mechanism to support the development of multiple vaccines and ensure their worldwide distribution. Through COVAX, Member States that would otherwise not have access to sufficient doses of vaccines were given the opportunity to protect at least part of their population, especially health workers and the most vulnerable groups. The program also encouraged different vaccine manufacturers to share their knowledge and technology, which further accelerated vaccine development and increased overall production volume. This type of cooperation is critical in the fight against the global pandemic and shows the importance of pooling efforts and resources to achieve a common goal.

- **International humanitarian aid:** Many countries and international organizations provided humanitarian aid and support to the most vulnerable countries and populations.

A specific example of countries that provided humanitarian aid during the COVID-19 pandemic are the following:

- **United States:** Through various federal agencies, including USAID, the United States has provided assistance to many countries around the world, including funding, medical equipment, and support to strengthen health systems. The motivation included both diplomatic and strategic interests as well as the global responsibility to deal with the pandemic.

- **China:** China implemented the so-called "mask diplomacy", sending medical supplies and aid to numerous countries in Europe, Africa and Asia. While this was presented as an act of solidarity, critics have discussed these efforts as a way to improve China's international image and increase geopolitical influence.

- **European Union:** The EU activated its Union Civil Protection Mechanism to coordinate and finance the delivery of medical equipment between member states and outside the Union. In addition, the EU supported the COVAX initiative by providing financial resources to support access to vaccines in poorer countries.

Russia: Providing aid in the form of its Sputnik V vaccine to a number of countries in Latin America, the Middle East and Asia, which was also discussed as part of the so-called "vaccine diplomacy", and was perceived as an attempt to strengthen diplomatic and economic ties and influence in these regions.

These examples show that the motivations behind the provision of humanitarian aid can be diverse and are often a combination of the desire to help with a view to global health and stability, as well as the desire to strengthen or expand geopolitical and diplomatic interests.

The COVID-19 pandemic is a challenge that has the potential to both divide and unite the international community. The reactions of different countries candidly highlight the dynamics of current geopolitical relations and show how crises can upend and reshape international relationships and priorities.

The information about COVID-19: Struggle for a dominant narrative

In the information age we live in, information flows have become a major factor in shaping public behavior and decisions. The COVID-19 pandemic accentuated this aspect even more, as in the battle against the virus, there was also a struggle for dominance of the information space.

The media and social platforms were the arena in which the struggle for information dominance was played out. They not only transmitted but also modeled information flows, shaping and guiding public discussions and reactions.

Information about COVID-19 has been subject to significant politicization. Different political forces and countries used the information to support their own agendas, interests and narratives, further compromising the objectivity and reliability of the information provided.

The struggle for a dominant narrative had profound ethical and social consequences, including ruptures in the social fabric, polarization and mistrust. This caused problems not only in the management of the health crisis, but also in social cohesion and democratic processes.

The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the need for responsible and ethical information management in crisis situations. The struggle for a dominant narrative has become a central element of the global response to the pandemic and requires serious analysis and reflection on future practices in information policy and communication during crises.

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